

CONSIDERATIONS REGARDING THE INFLUENCE OF ENTROPY IN ORGANIZATIONS. A MOUNTAIN VIEW

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3

Abstract

Understanding the nature of an organization poses challenges as conventional terms often fall short in capturing its existential reality. The limitations of relying solely on synonyms become apparent in such complex scenarios. Various terms, including entity, structure, relationship, mechanism, social complex, and form of administration, can be deemed synonymous with the concept of organization. However, relying on circular-synonymous-metaphorical definitions proves inadequate. While rejecting these definitions, no alternative comprehensive "versions" that offer a more encompassing understanding seem readily available. In the realm of mountain research, navigating the intricate paths of organizational definition requires exploring uncharted territories to uncover nuanced perspectives that transcend conventional linguistic boundaries.

Keywords: organizations, entropy, mountain research, social complex

1. Introduction

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In the realm of organizational dynamics, the influence of entropy — the measure of disorder or randomness — has become a subject of increasing interest and importance. Drawing inspiration from the formidable landscapes of mountainous regions, this article explores the considerations surrounding entropy in organizations and introduces a unique mountain research approach to dissecting its impact.

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4

The Metaphor of Mountains in Organizational Dynamics:

Mountains, with their rugged terrains, unpredictable weather patterns, and the constant interplay of forces, provide an evocative metaphor for the challenges organizations face in maintaining order and coherence. The ascent and descent along the organizational landscape share parallels with the peaks and valleys of a mountainous terrain, offering insights into the ebb and flow of entropy within organizational structures.

Etymologically, the noun "organization" traces its roots to "organon," signifying an instrument or tool (Morgan, 2006, p. 15). However, the etymology falls short in encapsulating the intricate and multifaceted meanings, neglecting a vital factor crucial for an exact definition.

In the realm of mountain research, before formulating a comprehensive definition, reflections on the nature of organization(s) become imperative. Questions pertaining to the ubiquity of organizations in the universe, their discovery or invention, and their status as a state or a fact warrant exploration. Delving into the evolutionary timeline, pondering if our world

ever existed without organizations, and examining the relationship between the multitude of organizations and complex societal development are crucial aspects.

5

Drawing parallels from the entropic systems prevalent in the natural world, we question whether organizations or organization are absent in such systems. Can we envision a state where organization is unnecessary, akin to absolute zero in the third principle of thermodynamics, where atomic activity ceases?

5

In the context of the human body, which is subject to entropy, the cells exhibit a robust anti-entropic force. Transposing this principle to organizational existence, we contemplate whether the environment is inherently entropic while the organization acts as an anti-entropic force.

Exploring the scope of organization beyond exclusively human creations, we ponder if organizations are Ex nihilo creations or mere artifacts. Considering the necessity of interaction in defining an organization, we question how many characteristics an entity must possess to be termed an "organization."

Addressing the interplay between organization and performance goals, we inquire if organizations can exist without achieving specific objectives. Identifying unique aspects that differentiate between organization and organization, such as legitimacy, the human element, goals, and performance, becomes a focal point in our mountainous exploration.
PSYCHO-SOCIAL VIEW JOURNAL (1/2021)

In the expansive landscape of organizational theory, this mountain research approach aims to navigate the uncharted territories, seeking nuanced perspectives that transcend conventional definitions and encapsulate the complexity inherent in the concept of organization.

2. Literature review

In the realm of mountain research focus, the question of why we organize finds resonance in Niklas Luhmann's perspective. According to Luhmann, the compelling force behind our need to organize is time. Time emerges as a precious constraint, compelling us to structure our endeavors to accomplish objectives within its finite boundaries. Luhmann contends that an abundance of time would render everything adaptable to anything else, eliminating the need for deliberate organization (Luhmann, 1995, pp. 41-42).

The consequence of time's scarcity is the necessity for selections. Faced with temporal constraints, we are compelled to make choices – deciding what falls within our sphere of control and what lies beyond our understanding. This process is integral to constructing our world, offering a semblance of relative stability within the constant flow of the world around us.

However, the elusive nature of time introduces complexity. While chronological periods provide a convenient definition of time, offering comfort through a clear scale for measurement, they also emphasize order

and predictability (Hernes, 2008, p. 85). In the context of mountain research, the analogy is akin to navigating the rugged terrain with a reliable map – offering a structured approach to comprehend and anticipate the challenges presented by the dynamic landscape of time.

7

7

In essence, the mountain research focus invites us to explore the intricate relationship between time and organization, emphasizing the role of temporal constraints in shaping the structures that provide stability within the ever-changing currents of the world.

3. Defining organizations. Research results

In the chronicles of organizational definitions, a panoramic view reveals shifting perspectives depending on the decade. The '60s marked an era where organizations were characterized in terms of goals, formal structures, and integrative approaches. The subsequent periods of the '70s and '80s witnessed a transition toward defining organizations in terms of human activities. Post the 1980s, a paradigm shift occurred, with organizations being delineated in terms of controlled performance (Zlate, 2004, p. 90). As we venture into the 21st century, organizations seem to gravitate toward definitions as interconnected entities, universal structures, hubs, or networks of entities and organizational subassemblies.

To decipher the essence of an organization, a mountain research approach involves identifying its common elements. Primarily, an organization is comprised of people, a sentiment echoed by Keyton (Keyton, 2005, p. 4). Drucker extends this perspective, defining an organization as a human group

PSYCHO-SOCIAL VIEW JOURNAL (1/2021)

of specialists collaborating towards a shared goal. Unlike traditional social aggregates such as "society," "community," or "family," organizations are intentionally designed entities, not anchored in either the psychic nature of humans or biological needs (Drucker, 1993, p. 43).

Various definitions contribute to the landscape of organizational understanding. It can be seen as "a group with a purpose" (J. Szczepanski as cited in Zlate, 2004, p. 83) or "a consciously coordinated social unit composed of two or more people, operating on a relatively continuous basis, to achieve a common goal or set of goals" (Robbins & Judge, 2013, p. 5). Organizations are depicted as entities striving for goals, with their success hinging on organizational structure or processes (Greenfield, 1973, p. 2). Rafaeli (1996, p. 2) characterizes organizations as open systems with a free flow of various resources transcending organizational boundaries.

Vlăsceanu (2003, p. 89) presents the organization as a group of people engaged in interactions oriented by common and specific objectives. Culda (1999, p. 43) describes organizations as partially explicit socio-organizations, constituted by the specialized collaboration of individuals to deliberately satisfy social needs. Recognizing the intentional nature of organization formation, Vlăsceanu (1993, p. 16) notes that organizations emerge when at least two conditions are met: people can communicate, and they willingly contribute to a common goal, necessitating coordination and cooperation.

In the vast terrain of organizational theory, these diverse perspectives contribute to a rich tapestry that reflects the complexity of defining organizations, akin to navigating the diverse landscapes of a mountain range.

4. Conclusions

In the realm of mountain research focus, the quest to define organizations encounters various overlaps and attempts to introduce new terms like bureaucracy, structures, and total institutions. These additions, while diversifying perspectives, may lead to confusion and offer distinct analytical angles that do not necessarily resolve the essential question: What is the organization?

The abundance of material amassed on organizations, though impressive in both quantity and quality, has not yielded a unified view. The persistent doubts surrounding the definition, description, analysis, classification, and interpretation of organizations prompt a critical inquiry. Zlate (2004, p. 81) points to three major causes contributing to this situation within the organizational landscape.

Firstly, the multitude of perspectives adopted in the analysis of organizations creates a fragmented understanding. This diversity of viewpoints, akin to navigating through varied terrains, introduces complexity and hinders the establishment of a cohesive definition. Each perspective offers a different vantage point, adding layers to the organizational landscape but also contributing to the lack of a unified view.

Secondly, the non-discriminatory use of certain concepts fosters confusion, ambiguities, and overlapping terms. Like a labyrinthine network of trails on a mountainside, the indiscriminate use of terminology complicates the path to a clear and concise definition. The proliferation of concepts without precise differentiation creates a landscape where the boundaries between terms blur, making it challenging to discern their distinct meanings.

Finally, Zlate identifies the sometimes-abusive use of metaphors in the design and interpretation of organizations as a contributing factor. Metaphors, like the diverse features of a mountainous terrain, can enrich understanding but can also lead to misinterpretations and further complicate the endeavor to establish a unified view of organizations.

In the pursuit of clarity and coherence, the mountain research focus emphasizes the need to navigate through these challenges, recognizing the diverse perspectives, clarifying conceptual boundaries, and critically assessing the use of metaphors to ensure a more unified and comprehensive understanding of the essence of organizations.

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